

FORMING ECOLOGICALLY CLEAN PRODUCTION MARKET IN TURKMENISTAN

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Modern economic theory no longer studies two levels of the economic system - micro- and macroeconomics, as it was in the last century, but five main levels: nano- (the level of a human worker), micro-, macro-, mega- and metaeconomics. Without such an approach, provision of sustainable development is impossible, especially since it is recognized by the world community as the most important direction for further growth. Sustainable Development Goals submitted by the United Nations came into force in January, 2016. They were adopted by world leaders in September 2015 at the historic UN summit. Over the next 15 years to achieve these universal goals, countries must intensify their efforts to end poverty in all its forms, fight inequalities, and address climate and environmental challenges.

One of the directions of achieving sustainable development goals is forming and developing ecologically clean production market, or organic agriculture. According to FAO, "organic agriculture is a holistic production management system which promotes and enhances agri-ecosystem health, including biodiversity, biological cycles, and soil biological activities. It emphasizes the use of Good management practices in preference to the use of off-farm sources, taking into account that regional conditions require locally adapted systems. This is accomplished by using, where possible, agronomic, biological, and mechanical methods, as opposed to using synthetic materials, to fulfil any specific function within the system".

Organic agriculture is rapidly developing and is becoming increasingly important in the agricultural sector of countries around the world, regardless of their level of development.

Currently, organic agriculture is practiced in 190 countries, and almost 75 million hectares of agricultural land are managed organically by at least 3.3 million farmers. Organic farming is cultivated in 190 countries from the North to the South pole. According to FiBL, the global organic food market reached 120 billion euros in 2020. The countries with the largest organic markets were the United States (49.5 billion euros), Germany (15.0 billion euros) and France (12.7 billion euros). The US is the leading market (49.5 billion euros), followed by Germany (12.0 billion euros) and France (11.3 billion euros). Many major markets continue to show high growth rates.

Organic agriculture is a socio-economic and food component focused on the preservation of the environment, well-being of people and animals. Organic agriculture is considered as one of the components of the sustainable development of Turkmenistan. When defining the goals of the long-term development of the Turkmen economy in the Program "Revival of a new era of a sovereign state: the National program of socio-economic development of Turkmenistan for 2022-2052" the tasks are set to maintain a stable sustainability of development, forming and developing the "green economy" while preserving natural capital. In this context the development of organic agriculture is especially important for Turkmenistan, as it can change the negative trends that have developed for decades and lay the foundations for sustainable development of rural areas.

Research have shown that the system of priority areas of the organizational and economic mechanism for the formation and sustainable development of organic farming in Turkmenistan includes: development and adoption of the regulatory framework necessary for the effective

functioning of the system of agricultural production and markets for environmentally friendly products; creation of a national system of certification, labeling and conditions for processing; organization of a centralized marketing service that ensures the promotion of products of domestic producers inside and outside the country; development of scientific support for this industry (biotechnology, ecological selection, etc.); providing consulting and information support, educational publications and programs to producers of organic products and the formation of an ecological culture of consumers; establishment of incentive measures and financial support for producers and processors.

Based on the conducted research and the study of existing experience, the following main stages for the transition of farms to organic production can be proposed.

First stage deals with monitoring and qualitative assessment of land and the natural environment to determine the possibility of conducting environmentally friendly management.

Second stage - training of heads and members of peasant (farm) enterprises on the issues of transition to a new type of production and the sale of environmentally friendly products.

Third stage deals with drawing up a business plan for the development of the economy with an economic analysis that will help to correlate costs and possible income, as well as in order to obtain state support.

Fourth stage is about certification procedure - certification of the quality management system for compliance of their products with international standards of organic agriculture and the right to use environmental labeling of goods.

In this context at the last stage, the conclusion of contracts with processing enterprises for the processing of organic raw materials and signing contracts for the sale of environmentally friendly products in the domestic and foreign markets.

Thus, in modern conditions and taking into account the current events, the transition of Turkmenistan to forming «green» economy is quite significant and relevant and can lead the country to a new round of development, occupy other economy's niches. One of the main directions of this concept is organic production development in agriculture. Organic agriculture in Turkmenistan is just beginning its development, which in the future would allow the republic to join the dynamically developing market of organic products. Further improvement of a comprehensive legislation, provision of state support to producers, training of qualified specialists, reduction of prices to the level accessible to numerous segments of the population would significantly increase the share of organic production in the country's economy.